

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE ECONOMIC BASIS OF AMIR TEMUR AND THE TIMURID STATE

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Annotation. This article explores and analyzes the centralized state structure of Amir Temur, the improvement of the socio-economic situation of the Kingdom, and economic relations.

Keywords: Amir Temur, temurians, economic life, social relations, trade, market.

I. Introduction. The empire, founded by Amir Temur, occupies a special place among the major empires of the world. Timur belongs to the category of great personalities who left a huge legacy in history. For this reason, there has been a lot of controversy and controversy in the thief of his personality and services in world history, it is happening and will continue further. In a corresponding way, countless works and pamphlets were created. In these sources, Amir Temur is recognized as a great commander, a commander, an incomparable politician, a wise man, a world-famous statesman, a skilled orator, a holder of such unique personal qualities. At the moment, the economic aspects of the sobriquet in its lush functioning have been overlooked by researchers. Indeed, the main thoughts and aspirations of the Sahibqironn are to expand and strengthen the glorious empire, to control the state, to maintain tranquility in vast territories, to appease rebellious and disobedient rebels, with meaningful and wise speech

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. There are a number of historical sources on the subject of research, where valuable information about the socio-economic life of the Kingdom and trade relations is found. For example, these issues are covered in the works of Nizamiddin Shomiy, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, Ghiyosiddin Khondamir, Mirkhand and others. "Historia Yazd" and "Jadi Yazd" (يزد بزدترجى تريخ) also feature the economic relations and markets of the Timurid period. In our opinion, it was economic issues that took a central place in the Blessed activities of Amir Temur. We want to provide two arguments as proof of our opinion. First, the unification of scattered feudal states, ensuring their independence by defeating the mustakamlakachi Mongols, the restoration of water structures in disrepair, the establishment of discipline and peace in mamldakat, its maintenance, construction and improvement work is carried out.

Amir Temur paid serious attention to the effective use of the principles of material stimulation of productive labor in the purpose of attracting the broad masses of people to socially useful labor activities and encouraging him to act in the interests of society and the kingdom. The efforts of sahibqiron to protect the population from excessive absenteeism taxes and the encroachment of some non-profit taxpayers, to restore dilapidated roads and canals and to build new ones, to provide it with work and income through the use of state treasury funds, care for the working-class country, extensive construction and improvement work were various manifestations of this material incentive. As a result of this wise policy,

harmony between the economic interests of society, the state and the laborious economic interests of came to the bazar, these interests were aimed at the main goal, that is, to build a solid great state, the economic foundation of which is things.

The fact that the Great Emir Temür paid a lot of attention to precisely economic problems in Public Administration testifies to the fact that he is a man of rare and unique intelligence and economic thinking.

Although he was completely unaware of modern macroeconomic policy theories, he acted with a good understanding that the development and future of his empire were primarily closely related to economic progress. This man amazes his mind. Because in the times when Amir Timur solved serious issues of economic development within his kingdom in his career, neither the science of political economy nor sufficient theoretical knowledge was yet created to formulate it. In the pre-Christian centuries (e.o. 445-355 yy.) the concept of "Economy", invented by the philosopher of antiquity, who lived and created it, was not without theoretical considerations, which were later reflected in the works of some sages(Plato, Aristotle, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Abu Nasr Farabi) who thought in this regardless.

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Timur, the founder of the vast empire, was tough, but very intelligent and capable of analytical thinking. Thanks to these qualities, he became the owner of the ability to make the only correct, rational decision even in the most difficult, extremely complex economic situations. In our opinion, these unique personal qualities played an important role in exalting the economic power of the kingdom.

First of all, his harshness prevents state property, the Treasury from the encroachment of greedy, treacherous ones.

Secondly, his ability to find the only correct solution to the problem with great intelligence in any difficult situation made it possible to continuously multiply property. Temur skillfully used all methods to help increase dynastic property: military power, diplomacy, strong control and incentive measures.

If we carefully analyze the life and historical path of Timur The Great, then all his efforts to exclude Movorounnahr from the Mongol occupation.

In our opinion, it is very important to clarify the conditions that prompted Amirtemur to occupy the territories of other countries and its original reasons.

It is fair to evaluate all the actions of the sahibqirah, from the occupation of Movorounnahr to the liberation of the invaders, as a great service aimed at achieving economic independence, peace in the land. But the apponents condemn the marches to other countries where the country was after independence. What was the main reason for Amir Temur's aggressive actions towards other lands: condemning the inhabitants of the occupied territories to depression, simply striving for political will and glory, or any other desires and incentives unknown to us? It seems to us that the main incentive that prompted Timur The Great to take such actions after Morounnahr gained independence was the economic interests of the country.

Conclusion. The tireless work of Amir Timur aimed at building a large centralized state also had a positive effect on the economic development of the countries included in the composition of the kingdom. More extensive Meditations by ukmdor are known in history, which may also have prompted him to make constant military campaigns:"there cannot be two Kings on the whole earth". In any case, the essence of Timur's philosophy is that there should not be two kings competing with each other for the purpose of owning economic resources in the world. Peace and tranquility prevail on Earth, and the arms race, which can destroy humanity several times, is also destroyed.

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